

SPECIAL SCIENCE SCHOOL SYSTEM (SSSS): IMPLEMENTATION AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) in public elementary and secondary schools in Valencia District, Bohol, Philippines, during the school year 2023-2024. It uses a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative survey questionnaires, qualitative key informant interviews (KIIs), and focus group discussions (FGDs) to completely analyze the amount of implementation and obstacles faced by school administrators and teachers. The findings reveal differences in perspectives between administrators and teachers, with administrators generally having more positive attitudes towards Special Science School System. Resource limits, time constraints, and reluctance to creative instructional practices are some of the challenges. Nonetheless, both groups emphasize the importance of cooperation, professional growth, and community connections in facilitating implementation. The study emphasizes the importance of continuous evaluation, specialized training, and longitudinal studies to track the program's progress and efficacy. The study recommends regular assessments, targeted professional development initiatives, and longitudinal research to ensure the SSSS's successful implementation and sustainability, to improve scientific education and contribute to the nation's sustainable development objectives.

Keywords: *Science education, Special Science School System*

INTRODUCTION

The ultimate aim of science education is to cultivate scientific literacy among learners, equipping them to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving global landscape. However, the Philippines faces substantial challenges in achieving this goal, as reflected in the country's performance in international assessments. Filipino students' achievements in science have consistently lagged behind their global peers, with the Trends International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2007 and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 indicating significant difficulties in basic scientific skills. Notably, the PISA 2018 report revealed that 81% of Filipino students struggled with fundamental math skills, reading comprehension, and scientific reasoning. This trend continued in the PISA 2022 results, where the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries, showing minimal improvement.

According to Parojenog and Pabalan (2024), despite ongoing efforts by the Philippine government to enhance education quality, the country is facing an educational crisis, particularly in science education, which is vital for personal and national development. The persistent gap in science achievements highlighted by TIMSS 2007 and PISA assessments underscores the urgent need for reforms in science education.

In response to these challenges, Philippine Basic Education emphasized the necessity for a revised curriculum that aligns with the nation's aspirations. This revised curriculum aims to develop lifelong learners with 21st-century skills, discipline, and patriotism. It seeks to prepare students for higher education, employment, and global competitiveness.

The Schools Division of Bohol (SDO-Bohol) introduced the Special Science School System (SSSS) to address these issues. This initiative includes elementary and secondary schools with advanced teachers and minimal facilities to support Special Science Classes (SSC). The SSSS is designed to offer enhanced science education to talented learners, fostering their skills in advanced subjects such as Enhanced Math, Enhanced Science, Creative Technology, and Science Research.

This study is grounded in three prominent curriculum evaluation models: Stake's Responsive Evaluation Model, the Context, Input, Process, Product (CIPP) Model, and Goal-Based Evaluation Theory. Stake's Responsive Evaluation Model, developed by Robert Stake in the 1970s, emphasizes addressing stakeholder needs and understanding diverse perspectives, supporting a collaborative approach to evaluating and improving the SSSS implementation. The CIPP Model, created by Daniel Stufflebeam in the 1987, provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating educational programs through context, input, process, and product components. This model will guide the assessment of the SSSS by analyzing contextual factors, evaluating resource adequacy, examining program delivery, and assessing overall effectiveness.

Based Evaluation Theory, pioneered by Ralph W. Tyler, focuses on evaluating the extent to which a program achieves its predetermined goals and objectives. This theory will be used to measure the SSSS's success in meeting its intended outcomes.

Division Memorandum No. 0322 series of 2023 and DepEd Order No. 55 series of 2010 provide legal support for this study. They outline policies and guidelines for strengthening science and mathematics education and ensuring that the SSSS adheres to national standards.

The implementation of the SSSS presents both opportunities and challenges. Previous studies, such as those by Montebon (2014) and Beasley (1999), highlight the potential of new programs to enhance learning but also emphasize the importance of careful implementation and continuous evaluation. Professional development for teachers and support from school administrators is crucial for the program's success. The research will draw insights from related studies by Atchuela (2019), Sumardani (2021), Bangcaya and Alejandro (2015), Macaranas and Robles (2023), Decenorioa et al. (2016), and Madani (2020) to address the challenges and opportunities in implementing the SSSS.

This research aimed to provide a comprehensive investigation into the implementation of the SSSS in the Valencia District of Bohol, focusing on how the special science classes were rolled out, the challenges encountered, and the program's overall impact. By identifying both the advantages and disadvantages of the SSSS, the study offered actionable recommendations for enhancing science education. The ultimate goal was to better prepare learners for science careers and contribute to sustainable national development. By leveraging theoretical frameworks and practical insights, this research provided valuable contributions to improving science education and supporting the development of scientifically literate individuals in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) in both elementary and secondary public schools within the Valencia District, while also identifying the challenges encountered during the initial stages of its implementation.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the SSSS as perceived by the administrators, and teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. curriculum implementation;
 - 1.2. instructional program; and
 - 1.3. instructional support?
2. What is the level of the challenges encountered by the school administrators, and teachers in implementing the SSSS in terms of:
 - 2.1. pedagogical content knowledge;
 - 2.2. curriculum and planning; and
 - 2.3. assessment and reporting?

3. Is there a significant difference between the administrators' and teachers' perceptions in terms of:
 - 3.1. extent of implementation; and
 - 3.2. level of challenges?
4. Based on the results of the study, what can be proposed to improve the implementation of the SSSS?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a concurrent parallel mixed-method approach, or triangulation design, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis. This mixed-method design was well-suited for investigating the new special science class program's implementation and challenges, as it provided a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem than qualitative or quantitative approaches alone.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at Valencia Technical Vocational High School (VTVHS) and Valencia Central Elementary School (VCES), both public schools in Poblacion Oriental, Valencia, Bohol. These schools, representing the entire district of Valencia, were approved for adopting the SSSS curriculum. Their selection was based on their capacity to offer the special science program by the requirements outlined by the division's supervision committee, following an on-site inspection and a thorough review of facilities and inventories.

Research Participants

The study focused on school administrators and teachers from public secondary and elementary schools as its main participants. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure key stakeholders were included in establishing the Special Science School System (SSSS). The sample comprised ten personnel from the district's participating schools, including two school principals, two program coordinators, a head teacher, and five master teachers. These individuals played crucial roles in overseeing and implementing the SSSS at their schools. Additionally, the study included all twenty teachers who represented the curriculum in Valencia's primary and secondary schools. These teachers were responsible for handling subjects within the Special Science Class (SSC) and adhering to the guidelines of the SSSS.

Table 1. Distribution of Participants of the Study.

Grade Level	School Administrators	Teachers	Total
Elementary (VCES)	5	8	13
Secondary (VTVHS)	5	12	17
Total	10	20	30

Research Instrument

The study employed a survey questionnaire, key informant interviews (KIIs), and focus group discussions (FGDs) to assess the implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS). The survey questionnaire, designed based on Macaranas and Robles (2023), evaluated curriculum implementation, instructional program effectiveness, and support systems. It measured participants' perceptions of SSSS implementation across three categories: curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and topic knowledge and pedagogy.

For qualitative insights, KIIs and FGDs used adapted guide questions from the survey to explore specific observations and challenges related to SSSS implementation. These guide questions addressed discrepancies in survey responses regarding implementation extent and encountered difficulties.

A panel of experts—the researcher's school principal III, the district's SSSS program coordinator, and a master teacher in science—reviewed the questionnaire to ensure its content validity. Their feedback led to refinements of the questionnaire. The researcher's thesis adviser also reviewed the final version to ensure it aligned with the research objectives.

To evaluate the instrument's clarity and effectiveness, a pilot test was conducted with 15 participants (5 school administrators and 10 science teachers) from a comparable district. Feedback from this pilot test was used to make further improvements.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher obtained permission for the study from the Schools Division Superintendent of Bohol. An endorsement letter was then sent to the selected school administrators. The science coordinator, master teachers, and head teachers were informed about the study to secure their support and guidance.

Prior to data collection, a request letter and manuscript were submitted to Holy Name University's Ethics Review Board (ERB) for ethical review. After receiving approval, the researcher adhered to the ERB's guidelines and protocols.

Survey questionnaires and focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted over a six-day period: two days for distribution, three days for completion, and one day for retrieval. Separate FGDs for administrators and teachers, each lasting 60 minutes, used open-ended questions to discuss SSSS implementation and challenges. FGDs were conducted impartially, and manual transcription of discussions ensured accuracy. Participants reviewed transcripts for transparency. Those unable to attend FGDs were interviewed via key informant interviews (KIIs).

Data Analysis

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative methods to ensure result validity and reliability. Quantitative data was organized and analyzed using Microsoft Excel for descriptive statistics and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for advanced analysis. T-tests compared mean scores between teachers and school administrators to identify significant differences in perceptions of SSSS implementation.

Qualitative data, being categorical, were analyzed using thematic analysis. This process involved transcribing data, generating codes to capture key responses and themes, and refining these codes through cross-referencing with transcripts. This approach enabled the integration of qualitative insights with quantitative survey results, providing a comprehensive understanding of the SSSS implementation.

Treatment of Data. The study used both quantitative and qualitative methods to evaluate the administrators' and teachers' assessed implementation levels of the Special Science School System (SSSS) and the difficulties they encountered during the initial year of operation.

The following are the statistical treatments that were employed in achieving the research objectives:

To determine both the extent of implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) and the level of challenges encountered throughout its implementation process, the researchers applied the weighted mean formula:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where :

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of frequencies and its weight

N = the number of participants

The computed weighted mean was interpreted using the following scales:

Scale	Description
3.26 - 4.00	Fully Implemented
2.51 - 3.25	Mostly Implemented
1.76 - 2.50	Partially Implemented
1.00 - 1.75	Not at all implemented

Scale	Description
4.21 - 5.00	Extremely Challenging
3.41 - 4.20	Very Challenging
2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Challenging
1.81 - 2.60	Slightly Challenging
1.0 - 1.80	Not at all challenging

In order to ascertain any meaningful distinctions between the perspectives held by administrators and teachers concerning the extent of the implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS), as well as their perceptions regarding the level of challenges faced during its implementation, the t-test formula was used:

$$t\text{-value} = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

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- $\bar{x}_1$: Mean value of the first group
 - $\bar{x}_2$: Mean value of the second group
 - n_1 : Size of the first group
 - n_2 : Size of the second group
 - s_1 : Standard deviation of the first group
 - s_2 : Standard deviation of the second group

Thematic analysis served as the qualitative method utilized to interpret the data obtained from the focus group discussions to distinguish the specific observations the administrators and teachers have about the implementation of SSSS, employing manual transcription to transcribe the spoken words into written text. Throughout this process, the administrators' and teachers' interview responses were carefully refined and merged, focusing on finding commonalities in their concepts. These combined answers were then arranged into discrete themes and descriptions that captured the main aspects of their perspectives. The final themes were collated, totaled, and evaluated in accordance with the issue statement, which made it possible to fully comprehend the data and enable more in-depth comprehension of the study goals.

RESULTS

This chapter discusses the school administrators' and teachers' responses which were summarized using descriptive statistics (weighted mean) and inferential statistics (t-test) for quantitative data. Content analysis was applied for qualitative data in which responses were organized according to themes. Discussion notes from transcriptions were woven into the form of narratives.

Table 2. Extent of Implementation in Curriculum Implementation.

Curriculum Implementation	Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
Admission – Meeting the standard admission policies that are clear and easy to follow based on the issuances and guidelines.	3.40	Fully Implemented	3.00	Mostly Implemented
Retention – Meeting the standard and clear policy in student retention in the program.	3.00	Mostly Implemented	2.95	Mostly Implemented
Curricular Programs – Complying with the learning competencies intended for Special Science School System (SSSS) implementing schools.	3.40	Fully Implemented	2.80	Mostly Implemented
Co-curricular Programs – Providing co-curricular programs that are clear, accepted by learners, and do not disrupt instructional time.	3.10	Mostly Implemented	2.65	Mostly Implemented
Composite Mean	3.23	Mostly Implemented	2.85	Mostly Implemented

LEGEND: 1.0-1.75 Not all Implemented; 1.76-2.50 Partially Implemented; 2.51-3.25 Mostly Implemented; 3.26-4.0 Fully Implemented

Table 2 shows the extent of implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) as perceived by the participants in terms of curriculum implementation.

The results indicate that administrators perceive a higher degree of curriculum implementation compared to teachers. Administrators rated the implementation with a weighted mean of 3.23, ranging from 3.00 to 3.40, suggesting they view it as meeting expectations from "mostly implemented" to "fully implemented." In contrast, teachers rated it lower, with a composite mean of 2.85, ranging from 2.65 to 3.00, indicating that while they view the SSSS implementation positively overall, some areas do not fully meet their expectations.

Regarding admission policies, administrators reported a higher level of implementation (weighted mean of 3.40) compared to teachers (3.00). Administrators emphasized fairness and thoroughness in admissions, using multiple assessment methods and ensuring inclusivity. In contrast, teachers expressed concerns about the lack of transparency and inadequate communication in the admissions process, noting that unclear guidelines and limited assessment procedures affect the effectiveness of student selection.

Both administrators and teachers rated retention rules and curricular programs reasonably well, though administrators gave slightly higher scores. Co-curricular

programs were rated lower by both groups, with administrators scoring 3.10 and teachers scoring 2.65, indicating a need for improvement to fully meet expectations.

These findings align with Atchuela's (2019) study, which also reported positive perceptions of curriculum implementation due to the effective application of objectives and instructional methodologies. The consistency of these results underscores the importance of these aspects in achieving successful curriculum implementation.

Table 3. Extent of Implementation in Instructional Program.

Instructional Program	Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
Faculty Development – Giving seminars and training attended by teachers are related to the needs of the special science school system.	2.70	Mostly Implemented	1.95	Mostly Implemented
Teachers Qualification – Ensuring that the academic preparation of the teachers matches the requirements of the curriculum.	3.60	Fully Implemented	2.85	Mostly Implemented
Instructional Strategy – Instructional activities that show systematic organization, implementation, and evaluation following a class size for quality and excellence through sound classroom management.	3.10	Mostly Implemented	2.75	Mostly Implemented
Composite Mean	3.13	Mostly Implemented	2.52	Mostly Implemented

LEGEND: 1.0-1.75 Not all Implemented; 1.76-2.50 Partially Implemented; 2.51-3.25 Mostly Implemented; 3.26-4.0 Fully Implemented

Table 3 presents the extent of the Special Science School System (SSSS) implementation in terms of the instructional program as perceived by administrators and teachers.

Administrators rated teachers' qualifications highest, with a weighted mean of 3.60, indicating they view this component as well-implemented. They emphasized the importance of professional development and qualified teachers for the Special Science Class (SSC), with one administrator noting, "We prefer teachers with academic skills, allowing only master teachers and those with advanced degrees to teach this class." Another administrator highlighted the need for action research among SSC teachers to enhance instruction. This underscores administrators' commitment to supporting continuous teacher improvement.

Teachers rated qualifications with a weighted mean of 2.85, reflecting their recognition of the importance of qualified educators, though slightly lower than administrators' ratings.

Both groups rated faculty development lowest, with administrators scoring 2.70 and teachers 1.95, indicating a belief in its implementation but also suggesting room for improvement.

Instructional strategies were rated similarly by both groups, around 3.10, indicating general agreement that these strategies are implemented effectively. Administrators emphasized their comprehensive approach to performance evaluation and support, including monitoring, feedback, and professional development. They also valued professional learning communities and mentorship.

The composite means are 3.13 for administrators and 2.52 for teachers, both within the "mostly implemented" range. Administrators generally perceived a higher level of implementation than teachers, though both groups identified areas for improvement. These results align with Sumardani's (2021) study, which also indicated effective teaching approaches, but highlighted faculty development issues not covered in that research, suggesting differing views on training and support.

Table 4. Extent of Implementation in Instructional Support.

Instructional Support	Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
Laboratory Facilities, Equipment, and Supplies – Providing appropriate lab equipment apparatuses, considering advances in science and technology which allow for small group work.	3.0	Mostly Implemented	2.55	Mostly Implemented
Library Facilities and Services – Providing relevant and updated book selections with extensive collection of science and math- oriented books which meet the demands of the special science school system program.	2.4	Mostly Implemented	2.20	Mostly Implemented
ICT Integration – Teachers develop science lessons by designing informative PowerPoint, web pages, flash animations, and digital video productions.	3.40	Fully Implemented	2.90	Mostly Implemented

Physical Facilities (School Site, Buildings, and Classrooms) – A well-planned campus with adequate buildings for the social, cultural, and sports activities of learners with enough tables, chairs, and technology.	3.20	Mostly Implemented	2.50	Mostly Implemented
Composite Mean	3.0	Mostly Implemented	2.54	Mostly Implemented

LEGEND: 1.0-1.75 Not all Implemented; 1.76-2.50 Partially Implemented; 2.51-3.25 Mostly Implemented; 3.26-4.0 Fully Implemented

Table 4 presents the extent of implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) as perceived by participants regarding instructional support. Overall, perceptions are positive but vary between administrators and teachers.

Both administrators and teachers rated laboratory resources as "mostly implemented," with weighted mean (WM) scores of 3.0 and 2.55, respectively. However, teachers' lower scores suggest areas needing improvement in laboratory equipment. Similarly, library services and facilities received moderate scores of 2.4 and 2.20, indicating challenges in maintaining current and relevant book selections.

Administrators perceived ICT tool usage in science lessons as "fully implemented," with a WM score of 3.40, reflecting their commitment to integrating technology and enhancing learning experiences. This contrasts with teachers, who emphasized the need for more interactive, experiential learning approaches to boost engagement. Teachers also highlighted the importance of collaborative professional learning communities, aligning with research on effective leadership and stakeholder involvement in education.

The data reveals a dynamic SSSS implementation process, underscoring the need for continuous adaptation to technological advancements. Both administrators and teachers agreed that physical facilities were "mostly implemented," with WM scores of 3.20 and 2.50, indicating the general adequacy of school infrastructure. This suggests that while the SSSS has made significant strides, ongoing professional development, and support are necessary to integrate technology and enhance instructional practices fully.

Table 5. Level of Challenges in Pedagogical Content Knowledge.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Administrators		Teachers	
<i>As an administrator/teacher, I face challenges in...</i>	WM	Description	WM	Description
1. Supporting teachers in applying knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	3.40	Moderately challenging	3.10	Moderately challenging

2. Ensuring teachers have extensive knowledge of content beyond their area of specialization.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.20	Moderately challenging
3. Encouraging teachers to motivate learners to investigate content to expand knowledge and satisfy curiosity.	3.30	Moderately challenging	3.30	Moderately challenging
4. Helping teachers make intra- and interdisciplinary content relationships.	3.20	Moderately challenging	3.30	Moderately challenging
5. Confirming teachers address content accurately aligned to discipline.	2.90	Moderately challenging	3.40	Moderately challenging
Composite Mean	3.18	Moderately challenging	3.26	Moderately challenging

Legend: 1.0-1.80 Not at all challenging, 1.81-2.60 Slightly challenging, 2.61-3.40 Moderately challenging, 3.41-4.20 Very Challenging; 4.21-5.0 Extremely challenging

Table 5 illustrates the perceived challenges administrators and teachers face in implementing the Special Science School System (SSSS) related to pedagogical content knowledge. Both groups reported similar difficulties, with weighted mean scores ranging from 2.90 to 3.40, indicating "moderately challenging" conditions.

Administrators found confirming teachers' alignment of content to discipline the least challenging, with a WM score of 2.90, while supporting teachers in applying content knowledge across curricula was the most challenging, with a WM score of 3.40. An administrator noted that the absence of centralized teaching materials and lack of prior training sessions hindered teachers' development, and another pointed out teachers' limited engagement in embracing new approaches. Administrators also reported being overwhelmed by other tasks, affecting their focus on supervising the SSSS.

Conversely, teachers viewed ensuring content accuracy and alignment with core ideas as the most challenging, with a WM score of 3.40. They struggled with balancing depth of understanding against curriculum coverage within tight time constraints and keeping up with evolving scientific knowledge. They also faced difficulties in integrating new discoveries into their teaching.

Both administrators and teachers faced challenges in assisting with intra- and interdisciplinary content relationships and motivating students, with a WM of 3.30. Overall, the composite mean scores for administrators and teachers were 3.18 and 3.26, respectively, reflecting a "moderately challenging" view of SSSS implementation in pedagogical content knowledge.

These findings align with studies by Atchuela (2019) and Macaranas and Robles (2023), highlighting the importance of effective implementation strategies and addressing

challenges in content alignment and application within specialized science education programs.

Table 6. Level of Challenges in Curriculum and Planning.

Curriculum and Planning	Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
1. Supporting sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements.	3.0	Moderately challenging	3.60	Very challenging
2. Ensuring teachers plan well-structured lessons connecting concepts.	3.30	Moderately challenging	3.15	Moderately challenging
3. Confirming teachers sequence activities to scaffold learning objectives.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.30	Moderately challenging
4. Helping teachers connect outcomes to previous and future learning.	2.80	Moderately challenging	3.25	Moderately challenging
5. Providing appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.25	Moderately challenging
Composite Mean	3.06	Moderately challenging	3.31	Moderately challenging

Legend: 1.0-1.80 Not at all challenging, 1.81-2.60 Slightly challenging, 2.61-3.40 Moderately challenging, 3.41-4.20 Very Challenging; 4.21-5.0 Extremely challenging

Table 6 presents the perceived challenges administrators and teachers face in implementing the Special Science School System (SSSS) concerning curriculum and planning.

There are notable differences in how administrators and teachers perceive these challenges. Administrators find supporting sequenced teaching and learning processes less difficult than teachers, who rate it as extremely challenging. Teachers struggle to relate outcomes to past and future learning, whereas administrators find this task less challenging. The composite mean scores of 3.06 for administrators and 3.31 for teachers indicate that both groups view curriculum and planning challenges as moderately challenging.

Administrators rated supporting sequenced teaching and learning processes as moderately challenging, with a weighted mean score of 3.0. They face difficulties in

collaborative planning due to varying faculty objectives and time constraints. One administrator highlighted the need for a more inclusive approach by stating, "Others like teachers and staff represent us in overseeing the new program."

In contrast, teachers found implementing sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements challenging, with a weighted mean of 3.60. Due to limited instructional time, teachers struggle to make science concepts relatable and face issues with rushed, superficial treatment of topics. This highlights the difficulty in balancing curriculum demands with maintaining instructional quality.

Weighted mean scores ranging from 2.80 to 3.30 reflect challenges from "moderately challenging" to "very challenging." Administrators rated assisting teachers in connecting results to past and future learning moderately challenging (WM = 2.80), while teachers found it more challenging (WM = 3.25). Both groups agreed that planning well-structured lessons and sequencing activities to support learning objectives were relatively challenging, with a WM of 3.30.

The differing perceptions between administrators and teachers on various curriculum and planning difficulties align with findings from Macaranas and Robles (2023) and Atchuela (2019), which emphasize the need to address challenges in curriculum planning and implementation within specialized science education programs.

Table 7. Level of Challenges encountered in Assessment and Reporting.

Assessment and Reporting	Administrators		Teachers	
	WM	Description	WM	Description
<i>As an administrator/teacher, I face challenges in...</i>				
1. Implementing diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments consistent with curriculum.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.20	Moderately challenging
2. Supporting teacher use of assessment strategies for learner self-monitoring.	2.90	Moderately challenging	3.35	Moderately challenging
3. Ensuring assessments are embedded and aligned with content standards.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.25	Moderately challenging
4. Monitoring and evaluating learner progress and achievement.	3.0	Moderately challenging	3.20	Moderately challenging

5. Facilitating communication of learners' progress to stakeholders.	3.10	Moderately challenging	3.20	Moderately challenging
Composite Mean	3.04	Moderately challenging	3.24	Moderately challenging

Legend: 1.0-1.80 Not at all challenging, 1.81-2.60 Slightly challenging, 2.61-3.40 Moderately challenging, 3.41-4.20 Very Challenging; 4.21-5.0 Extremely challenging

Table 7 outlines the perceived challenges faced by administrators and teachers in implementing the Special Science School System (SSSS) related to assessment and reporting. Both groups view these challenges as moderately difficult, with composite mean scores of 3.04 for administrators and 3.24 for teachers.

Teachers identified using assessment strategies for learner self-monitoring as the greatest challenge, with a weighted mean of 3.35. Administrators, however, rated this challenge as the least difficult, with a weighted mean of 2.90. Other challenges, such as integrating assessments with content standards and communicating learner progress to stakeholders, were similarly rated by both groups, with mean scores of 3.10 to 3.25.

Further insights from key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs) reveal that administrators face logistical issues, such as ensuring access to necessary resources and managing various administrative tasks, which impact the assessment process. Conflicts and resource constraints also hinder effective teacher-student conferences and the monitoring of student performance.

Teachers highlighted the need for adaptive teaching methods to address varying levels of prior knowledge among students, emphasizing the importance of differentiated instruction and engaging assessment strategies. These challenges underscore the need for ongoing support and professional development to enhance assessment practices within the SSSS.

These findings align with Sumardani's (2021) study, which stresses the importance of addressing assessment challenges and ensuring conformity with content standards for effective SSSS implementation.

Table 8. Difference between participants' perceptions on implementation.

Variable	Mean±SD	Computed T-value	P-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Extent of Implementation of administrators & teachers	Teacher: 2.65±0.35 Administrator: 3.12±0.34	-7.03	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 8 shows a significant difference between administrators' and teachers' perceptions of the Special Science School System (SSSS) implementation. Administrators reported a higher mean perception score (3.12 ± 0.34) compared to teachers (2.65 ± 0.35). The computed t-value of -7.03 and p-value of 0.003 indicate statistical significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This suggests that administrators perceive a higher extent of SSSS implementation than teachers. The discrepancy may be due to administrators' broader oversight and access to institutional data, which influences their view of implementation effectiveness. In contrast, teachers are more focused on daily classroom issues and interactions. Administrators have access to additional information, such as resource distribution and professional development programs, which shapes their understanding of the SSSS implementation.

Table 9. Difference between participants' perceptions on the level of challenges.

Variable	Mean $\pm$ SD	Computed T-value	P-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Level of challenges of administrators & teachers	Teacher: 3.27 $\pm$ 0.12 Administrator: 3.09 $\pm$ 0.14	3.27	0.013	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 9 reveals a significant difference between administrators' and teachers' perceptions of the challenges encountered in implementing the Special Science School System (SSSS). Teachers reported a higher mean score of 3.27 compared to administrators' mean score of 3.09. The computed t-value of 3.27 and p-value of 0.013 indicate statistical significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This difference suggests that teachers view the challenges of implementing the SSSS as more significant than administrators do. This disparity reflects the distinct experiences and roles of the participants, with teachers having a more nuanced understanding of the obstacles due to their direct involvement in curriculum delivery and instruction. Teachers face practical difficulties in the classroom that administrators may not encounter firsthand.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The following are the highlights of the study:

1. Administrators and teachers have differing perspectives on the extent of the implementation of the SSSS. Teachers report a lower mean of 2.65, indicating a less favorable view, but administrators report a higher mean of 3.12, indicating a relatively strong assessment of implementation. Specifically,

- 1.1. In terms of curriculum implementation, administrators generally rated the implementation higher than teachers across various aspects such as admission policies, retention rules, curricular programs, and co-curricular programs with a composite mean of 3.23 for administrators and 2.85 for teachers. The lower composite mean from teachers indicates that some areas fell short of their expectations.
- 1.2. In terms of the instructional program, both groups prioritized teachers' qualifications. Administrators scored it as "fully implemented" with a composite mean of 3.60, while teachers, rated it as "mostly implemented" with a composite mean of 2.85. This highlights mutual acknowledgment and recognition that ensuring teachers' academic preparation coordinates with the curriculum requirements is critical for effective SSSS implementation.
- 1.3. In terms of instructional support, administrators and teachers generally perceived the implementation positively, with some variations. The composite mean for instructional support was 3.0 for administrators and 2.54 for teachers. The divergence of perceptions stems from differing vantage points of school administrators and teachers. The variation stresses the need for continued efforts in bridging the gap between organizational aspirations and classroom realities.
2. The level of challenges encountered by school administrators and teachers in implementing the Special Science School System (SSSS) is perceived to be moderately challenging, with administrators rating the challenges slightly lower with a mean of 3.09 than teachers with a mean of 3.27. Specifically,
 - 2.1. In terms of pedagogical content knowledge, both administrators and teachers rated the challenges with a composite mean of 3.18 and 3.26, respectively. The contrast in the identification of the most challenging task underscores the varying priorities among participants in which school administrators focused on cross-curricular integration while teachers grappled with the complexities of content delivery.
 - 2.2. For curriculum and planning, administrators rated the challenges with a composite mean of 3.06, while teachers rated them slightly higher at 3.31. It was easier for school administrators to support sequenced teaching and learning processes than teachers who find it extremely difficult. The contradiction of perceptions reveals different realities faced by administrators focusing on curricular alignment while teachers were occupied with the integration of conceptual understanding across learning experiences.
 - 2.3. In assessment and reporting, administrators and teachers rated the challenges with composite means of 3.04 and 3.24, respectively. Results highlight the need for professional development and resource allocation, empowering teachers with strategies to integrate monitoring assessments.
3. There is a significant difference between the administrators' and teachers' perceptions of the extent of implementation of the SSSS. Administrators conveyed a higher mean perception score (3.12 ± 0.34) compared to teachers

(2.65 ± 0.35). The computed t-value of -7.03 and the p-value of 0.003 indicate statistical significance.

4. There is a significant difference between the administrators' and teachers' perceptions of the level of challenges encountered in the implementation of the SSSS. Administrators reflected a lower mean perception score (Mean±SD: 3.09±0.14) compared to teachers' (Mean±SD: 3.27±0.12). The computed t-value of 3.27 and a p-value of 0.013 indicate statistical significance.

Conclusions

The implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) in qualified schools was a significant milestone, with the introduction of transparent admission rules, efficient screening processes, and inclusive admission practices. However, the implementation process was not without obstacles. Resource restrictions, time constraints, and reluctance to innovative educational methodologies surfaced as major roadblocks. Despite these challenges, administrators and teachers emphasized teamwork, professional development, and community collaborations to improve the implementation process emphasizing the necessity of adaptability and ongoing support in overcoming obstacles and ensuring the successful implementation of the SSSS program. It indicates that implementation techniques must be evaluated and refined on an ongoing basis to handle emerging issues and maximize the SSSS's efficacy in improving scientific education.

Recommendations

The following are hereby recommended:

1. School administrators in the Division Office should undertake regular assessments of the SSSS implementation process to monitor perception changes and address differences between administrators and teachers. Surveys, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews can be used to acquire qualitative information on their thoughts.
2. Administrators and teachers should be provided with specialized professional development opportunities to address specific implementation problems. Workshops, seminars, and training sessions can focus on curriculum preparation, instructional methodologies, and collaborative practices to help teachers apply the SSSS more effectively.
3. Other schools or districts that are planning or already implementing the SSSS should establish mechanisms for continuous feedback, monitoring, and evaluation. Regular assessment and collaborative analysis can facilitate a shared problem-solving approach that enhances the quality and effectiveness of the SSSS implementation.
4. Future researchers should consider undertaking longitudinal studies to monitor the progress and efficacy of SSSS adoption over time. By gathering data at numerous periods in time, researchers can obtain insight into the program's

sustainability, detect developing difficulties, and assess the long-term impact on student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Any ethical concerns that could have risen throughout the study were resolved by securing necessary permits. Also, the researcher personally handed the research tools to the schools, with the assistance of the administrators, which included the informed consent form and questionnaires. Before data collection began, all research terms and conditions were fully disclosed to maintain transparency. Despite receiving clearance from the school principals and administrators, the researcher obtained informed consent from participants by individually requesting them to participate and providing thorough information about the study, including potential risks and benefits, as well as privacy safeguards. Each participant was asked to review and sign the informed consent form, indicating their comprehension and willingness to be involved in the study. It was optional to provide the participants' names, which were coded to preserve their identity. To safeguard data, further confidentiality measures were put in place, such as limiting access to physical and electronic resources. The study closely followed data privacy and research ethics guidelines, and participants were made aware of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment without facing consequences.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

Rationale

The Department of Education initiated the implementation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) aimed at advancing science education within the region's secondary schools (DepEd Order No. 55 series 2010). Although significant progress has been made, there are still underlying issues that need to be addressed in order to guarantee the program's long-term viability and effectiveness. The developmental plan that has been suggested aims to tackle these obstacles and use prospects to improve the execution of the SSSS.

Through a strategic emphasis on critical domains such as the need for clearer admission requirements, diverse screening processes, and enhanced faculty support. These insights emphasize the importance of refining existing practices and fostering a collaborative environment to overcome implementation hurdles and ensure the program's success. The plan aims to cultivate an atmosphere that promotes program success and students' overall growth. The strategy prioritizes these areas in an effort to foster an atmosphere that will facilitate the successful implementation of the SSSS. The school offering Special Science Class (SSC) may overcome obstacles and fully implement the SSSS, boosting scientific instruction and supporting learners' holistic development, by working together and implementing focused interventions.

Objectives

The primary goal of this Enhancement Program is to improve the operation of the Special Science School System (SSSS) in implementing schools by focusing on critical areas for development. Specifically, the initiative seeks to:

1. Create and implement targeted professional development programs for teachers to improve instructional methodologies, classroom management approaches, and methods for engaging unmotivated learners;
2. Provide a forum for continued dialogue and cooperation amongst community people, educators, parents, and school administration to address issues, get input, and promote a feeling of responsibility and support for the SSSS implementation;
3. Give administrators access to mentorship and leadership development programs to improve their capacity to oversee implementation processes, resolve issues, and foster a welcoming and inclusive school environment that promotes student achievement; and
4. Prioritize areas that administrators and teachers have recognized as vital when evaluating resource allocation and usage methods to ensure adequate provision of materials, technology, and support services required for successful SSSS implementation.

Matrix

Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeframe	Success Indicators
Create and implement targeted professional development programs for teachers	1. Conduct needs assessment to identify areas for improvement in instructional methodologies	School administrators, Department of Education	3 months	Increased teacher competency in identified areas
	2. Develop curriculum for professional development workshops	Curriculum developers, Teacher trainers	2 months	Completion of workshop curriculum
	3. Facilitate workshops and training sessions	Facilitators, Subject matter experts	Year round	Attendance and participation rates
	4. Provide follow-up support and resources for continued professional growth	Teachers, Professional development coordinators	Year round	Feedback from teachers on usefulness of support
Provide a forum for continued dialogue and cooperation amongst stakeholders	1. Establish regular meetings or forums for stakeholders to discuss SSSS implementation issues	School administrators, Teachers, Community members	Year round	Increased collaboration and communication
	2. Encourage active participation and feedback from all stakeholders	Facilitators, Moderators	Year round	Number of meetings held, attendance rates

	3. Implement mechanisms for collecting and addressing concerns raised during meetings	School administrators, Department of Education	Year round	Timely resolution of issues raised
Give administrators access to mentorship and leadership development programs	1. Identify experienced mentors or leadership coaches to provide guidance and support	Department of Education, Experienced teachers	1 month	Availability of mentors/ coaches, selection criteria
	2. Develop leadership training curriculum focusing on oversight, issue resolution, and inclusivity	Curriculum developers, Leadership trainers	2 months	Completion of curriculum development
	3. Facilitate leadership training sessions	Trainers, Facilitators	Year round	Attendance and participation rates
	4. Provide ongoing support and feedback for administrators' growth and development	Teachers, Professional development coordinators	Year round	Feedback from administrators on usefulness of support
Prioritize areas for resource allocation and usage based on identified needs	1. Conduct comprehensive evaluation of current resource allocation and usage practices	School administrators, Department of Education	2 months	Identification of areas for improvement
	2. Gather input from teachers and administrators on resource needs and challenges	School administrators, Teachers	1 month	Feedback from stakeholders on resource allocation
	3. Develop revised resource allocation plan addressing identified needs and challenges	Resource allocation committee	1 month	Completion of revised resource allocation plan
	4. Implement revised resource allocation plan and monitor effectiveness	School administrators, Department of Education	Year round	Improved access to necessary resources

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